

A photovoltaic system using supercapacitor energy storage for power equilibrium and voltage stability

Savari R. Sahaya Prabaharan¹, Adamu Murtala Zungeru², Bokani Mtengi², Siluvai M. Michael³

¹Sathyabama Centre for Advanced Studies, Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai, India

²Department of Electrical, Computer and Telecommunications Engineering, Botswana International University of Science and Technology, Palapye, Botswana

³Chemical Sciences Research Centre, Department of Chemistry, Sri Sivasubramaniya Nadar College of Engineering, Tamilnadu, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received May 30, 2022

Revised Sep 5, 2022

Accepted Sep 11, 2022

Keywords:

Energy storage

Supercapacitors

Photovoltaic power systems

Power system stability

Voltage stability

ABSTRACT

In a photovoltaic system, a stable voltage and of tolerable power equilibrium is needed. Hence, a dedicated analog charge controller for a storage system which controls energy flow to impose power equilibrium, and therefore, voltage stability on the load is required. We demonstrate here our successful design considerations employing supercapacitors as main energy storage as well as a buffer in a standalone photovoltaic system, incorporating a dedicated supercapacitor charge controller for the first time. Firstly, we demonstrated a photovoltaic system employing supercapacitors as main energy storage as well as a buffer in a standalone photovoltaic system. Secondly, we design a constant voltage maximum power point tracker (MPPT) for peak power extraction from the photovoltaic generator. Thirdly, we incorporated a supercapacitor charge controller for power equilibrium and voltage stability through a dedicated analog charge controller in our design, the first of its kind. Fourthly, we analyzed the use of supercapacitor storage to mitigate disequilibrium between power supply and demands, which, in turn, causes overvoltage or under voltage across the load. Lastly, we then went ahead to demonstrate the control of the energy flow in the system so as to maintain rated voltage across a variant demand load.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Adamu Murtala Zungeru

Department of Electrical, Computer and Telecommunications Engineering, Botswana International University of Science and Technology

Private Bag 16, Palapye, Botswana

Email: zungerum@biust.ac.bw

1. INTRODUCTION

Mitigating the effects of fossil fuel burning is of great interest worldwide. Renewable energy holds the key to sustainable generation. Solar energy is one such form of energy available wherever there is sunlight and is expected to be a major clean energy provider in the near future. Photovoltaic (PV) power systems are usually installed as standalone systems, where the PV generator supplies an isolated load, or as grid-connected systems, where the PV generator and load are linked to a larger grid to which excess power can be sold or from which extra power can be bought.

Power output from a PV panel or array of PV panels is dependent on temperature and irradiance conditions. High irradiances and low temperatures are beneficial for more power. Load conditions also affect power output of a PV array, resulting in the need for a maximum power point tracker (MPPT) to extract the highest possible power irrespective of load, thus increasing efficiency.

Furthermore, as with all electric power systems, power stability is a concern in PV systems. Disequilibrium between load demand and supply from the PV generator results in overvoltage or undervoltage across the load. A storage system is able to alleviate the problem by absorbing the imbalances between supply power and demand, thus providing voltage stability.

However, maximum power point (MPP) tracker is important factor to be considered in this research. The current-voltage and power-voltage characteristics of a typical PV panel are such that the rated maximum power can be obtained at only one bias point, called the maximum power point and the equation is given by (1). Figure 1 illustrates this, where V_{mpp} , I_{mpp} , and P_{mpp} are the voltage, current, and power, respectively, at the MPP

$$P_{mpp} = V_{mpp}I_{mpp} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Magnetization current-voltage and power-voltage characteristics of a typical PV panel

The bias point, and therefore the power output, of the PV panel depend upon the load connected across it. Thus, an arbitrary load will not necessarily bias for maximum power. An MPPT is an interface connecting PV generator to load. Its task is to bias the input PV panel or array at the MPP, and supply this to any load connected to its output. The basic component of a MPPT is a power electronic converter. The type of converter and the control scheme employed varies with system requirements. At least 19 distinct control methods have been identified, varying in complexity, effectiveness, and cost [1]. Many algorithms use approximations to determine the maximum power point; for example, the fractional open-circuit voltage [2]–[4] and the fractional short-circuit current [5]–[7] methods, which are voltage and current-based methods, respectively. Other algorithms are more precise, such as hill-climbing [8]–[10], perturb-and-observe [11]–[14] and incremental conductance [15]–[17]; these are power-based algorithms. Various implementations of these algorithms exist, with novel methods being constantly developed. Most are digital microcontroller or fuzzy logic systems, while analog methods are less common [1].

In supercapacitors for storage, system instability occurs when supply power from the PV generators and load demand is not matched. Such conditions are dangerous to loads. Implementation of storage systems to absorb the imbalances is a solution, and is crucial in stand-alone PV systems, i.e., with no grid connection. Batteries are common storage devices but are susceptible to damage from fast charging and discharging and

have short lifetimes. Supercapacitors, on the other hand have such high-power densities that they can tolerate fast charge and discharge with no detrimental effects. This high-power tolerance, their long lifetimes, and low series resistance promise to make them ideal energy storage solutions in a PV system suffering from frequent and significant power imbalances. Supercapacitor technology is relatively new, and its incorporation into many systems is still under evaluation. Many papers have presented supercapacitors as power devices in electric vehicles [18], and some work has been done on their use in uninterrupted power supplies [19]. Supercapacitors are also undergoing tests as storage devices in power grids for improvement of grid performance and financial gains [20], [21]. They have been successful as voltage compensation units in electric transportation networks in Cologne, Germany [22]. In renewable energy systems, supercapacitors are used to increase the lifetime of the primary battery storage, which is affected by fast power fluctuations [23]. Diarra *et al.* [24] presents a simple scheme to connect a supercapacitor module as energy storage in a PV system in order to maintain direct current (DC) bus voltage.

Furthermore, optimization of battery life for energy storage systems is key to the cost reduction of renewable energy sources. Various design systems employ supercapacitors as a potential solution to improving battery life [25]–[30]. MPPT techniques are implemented to detect and measure maximum power output parameters automatically; V_{mpp} and I_{mpp} under particular irradiance and temperature conditions. The report notes that for partial shading conditions, although it is possible to have multiple local maxima, there is only one true technique of MPP. Compared to batteries, supercapacitors have high power capability, making them applicable for energy storage in PV systems. In other literature, researchers proposed control and optimization mechanisms to achieve power stability. In [31], the bat-inspired algorithm (BAT) and gravitational search algorithm (GSA) are proposed to design model predictive controllers with superconducting magnetic energy storage and capacitive energy storage for load frequency control. The proposed mechanism is used to minimize frequency deviations in multi-area power system. A new design using a proportional integral derivative (PID) controller based on meta-heuristic algorithms for wind energy conversion using the whale optimization system to control generator speed deviations due to the penetration of wind speed and load demand fluctuations [32]. To regulate frequency and achieve power stability in electrical grids, [33] proposed a new variable structure gain scheduling (VSGS), taking advantage of the bacterial foraging optimization algorithm (BFOA) based proportional integral (PI) controller and the genetic algorithm (GA). Control strategies for optimum utilization of solar PV with energy storage systems are implemented in [34]. Power management is achieved through the development of a variable DC bus voltage-based algorithm with supercapacitor and battery. A modified noniterative incremental conductance MPPT method is developed to generate a fine-tuned duty cycle for sudden irradiance changes. In [35], power management and control of the PV system are achieved by implementing a hybrid battery-supercapacitor energy storage based on heuristics methods. Control of the power electronics converters. Optimizing a multi-source PV/wind with a hybrid energy storage system is proposed using a multi-objective-based genetic algorithm [36]. However, to the best of our knowledge, none of the stated approaches considered our proposed solutions, of design considerations employing supercapacitors as main energy storage as well as a buffer in a standalone photovoltaic system, incorporating a dedicated supercapacitor charge-controller, first of its kind. Over the years, many studies have investigated photovoltaic systems and their applications in standalone systems. We have compared some of the promising techniques and applications in Table 1.

This paper presents a stand-alone PV system supplying a resistive load that requires a rated DC voltage of 12 V. An analog constant-voltage MPPT is designed for the photovoltaic array, and is coupled with a supercapacitor energy buffer bank (SEBB), with a dedicated analog charge controller for the bank which controls energy flow to impose power equilibrium, and therefore, voltage stability, on the load. The circuits for these systems are given and explained, and the results of simulations carried out on Cadence OrCAD Capture are presented. The simulations involve varying the load demand and observing the performance of the system as it reverses the resulting rises and falls in load voltage. In summary, our contributions in this paper are as follows: i) we demonstrated a photovoltaic system employing supercapacitors as main energy storage as well as a buffer in a standalone photovoltaic system; ii) we design a constant voltage MPPT for peak power extraction from the photovoltaic generator; iii) we incorporated a supercapacitor charge controller for power equilibrium and voltage stability through a dedicated analog charge controller in our design, first of its kind; iv) we analyzed the use of supercapacitor storage for mitigation of disequilibrium between power supply and demands, which, in turn, causes overvoltage or under voltage across the load; and v) lastly, we then demonstrate the control of the energy flow in the system so as to maintain rated voltage across a variant demand load.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In section 2, we first described the methods adopted for the research. In section 3, we present the results and discussions of the results obtained from the proposed methods. Concluding remarks are presented in section 4.

Table 1. Comparison of related work

Title	Citations	Year	Description	Pros	Cons	The uniqueness of this paper
Power management and control of a photovoltaic system with hybrid battery-supercapacitor energy storage based on heuristics methods	[35]	2021	Power management and control of the PV system which is achieved by implementing a hybrid battery-supercapacitor energy storage based on heuristics methods	Investigation of control and power management of hybrid energy storage system	The approached did not consider the use of supercapacitors for power equilibrium.	This paper considered the use of supercapacitors for power equilibrium.
New variable structure control based on different meta-heuristics algorithms for frequency regulation considering nonlinearities effects	[33]	2020	To regulate frequency and achieve power stability in electrical grids, the authors proposed a new variable structure gain scheduling (VSGS), taking advantage of the bacterial foraging optimization algorithm (BFOA) based PI controller and the genetic algorithm (GA).	Improvement on the gain selection of the proportional integral controller.	Voltage stability method was not properly considered	The design and implementation of voltage stability through a dedicated analog charge controller.
New design of robust PID controller based on meta-heuristic algorithms for wind energy conversion system	[32]	2020	A new design using a PID controller based on meta-heuristic algorithms for wind energy conversion using the whale optimization system to control generator speed deviations due to the penetration of wind speed and load demand fluctuations	Design of a robust PID controller for enhancing the damping characteristics of wind energy conversion system.	The design is specific for wind energy and not tested for other energy harvesting techniques.	Design of energy storage for power equilibrium and a dedicated analog charge controller for voltage stability.
Implementation of control strategies for optimum utilization of solar photovoltaic system with energy storage systems	[34]	2020	Control strategies for optimum utilization of solar PV with energy storage systems are implemented in the paper. A modified noniterative incremental conductance MPPT method is developed.	Power management is achieved through the development of a variable DC bus voltage-based algorithm with supercapacitor and battery.	The paper did not implement a novel voltage stability method.	This paper considers voltage stability through a dedicated analog charge controller.
Multi-objective genetic algorithm-based sizing optimization of a stand-alone wind/PV power supply system with enhanced battery/supercapacitor hybrid energy storage	[36]	2018	Optimizing a multi-source PV/Wind with a hybrid energy storage system is proposed using a multi-objective-based Genetic Algorithm.	Minimization of total cost and loss of power supply probability of the load using genetic algorithm.	Did not consider the voltage stability and power equilibrium in their design	Design of energy storage for power equilibrium and a dedicated analog charge controller for voltage stability

2. METHOD

This section described the procedures and methods adopted in carrying out this research. It is further subdivided into subsections. The system design elaborates on the modeling and steps followed to achieve the main design of the proposed method. MPPT and the MPPT simulation results were also presented in this section.

2.1. System design

The basic layout of the standalone PV system is given in Figure 2, with arrows indicating flow of power. The MPPT and charge controller are entirely analog in design. The load is resistive in nature, and is assumed to require 12 V DC. Thus, the load demand varies according to (2):

$$P_{demand} = \frac{(V_{rated})^2}{R_{load}} = \frac{(12V)^2}{R_{load}} \quad (2)$$

where P_{demand} : demand power (W), V_{rated} : rated load voltage (V), and R_{load} : load resistance (Ω).

The PV array modeled has MPP of 60 W at 24 V, and this is assumed to be invariable during operation. Hence, a constant-voltage MPPT is suitable for this array. The supercapacitor used in the SEBB is the CAP-XX GS206, 0.55 F, 5 V, 40 mΩ ESR; they are connected as parallel sets with two series-connected supercapacitors in each set. The charge controller adjusts the flow of energy in and out of the SEBB in order to regulate load voltage at 12 V.

System instabilities are created by setting R_{load} value such that P_{demand} is not equal to the supply power from the array, which is processed by the MPPT. When demand is less than supply, an overvoltage occurs across the load. An undervoltage occurs when demand exceeds supply. The role of the charge controller is to force excess supply power into the SEBB when overvoltage occurs and provide extra power from the SEBB to the load when undervoltage occurs. Either response should be controlled to re-achieve 12 V at the load.

Figure 2. PV system layout

2.2. PV array

The array modeled has a rated maximum power of 60 W at 24 V. For simplicity, it is assumed that the array can provide 60 W at 24 V indefinitely, i.e. the environmental conditions are ideal always. Figure 3 shows the array model constructed on Capture. While the characteristics of the array are illustrated in Figure 4.

2.2.1. Solar radiation hours and photovoltaic array sizing

In this paper, the idea of peak solar hours is introduced, in accordance with [37], and preliminary work reported in [38], for the temperature of the cells at 25 °C, equal to the average temperature of the Palapye in the central district of Botswana. Let's now consider the actual irradiance profile for a particular day as $X(t)$ at which the irradiance of the equivalent $x(t)$ is 1 KW/m² during a time of peak solar radiation hours (PSRH). It then implies that, the total daily radiation for the day is:

$$\int_{day} X(t)dt = 1 \cdot PSRH \quad (3)$$

The solar cell in consideration has a maximum current of 2.5 A and 24 V of voltage, similar to the report in [37]–[39] is as (4) and (5).

$$\int_{day} P_{max}(t)dt = 0.1982 \text{ KWh per day} \quad (4)$$

$$60W \times PSRH = 60W \times 3.25h = 195 \text{ Wh/day} \quad (5)$$

This work look into the worst-case scenario, for which the temperature is low to about 15 °C in addition to low irradiance values. In this work, the PSRH and energy balance relationship is (6).

$$P_{G-Nom}PSRH = L_E \quad (6)$$

where P_{G-Nom} is the nominal output power of the photovoltaic system for a standard condition [37], L_E the consumed energy over the average day by the load in the worst case. We utilize the procedures as outlined in our previous research as contained in [37] for the reminder design procedures.

In this work, we consider the whole building of load consumption of 7,500 Wh per day at 24 V. Each of the solar panels has the following ratings:

$$P_{SP} = 60W; \quad V_{OC} = 44.60V, \quad I_{SC} = 1.2A, \quad I_{MP} = I_{GM} = 0.82A, \quad V_{MP} = V_{GM} = 36.5V$$

We then compute the required current drawn by the load over the entire day as (7).

$$I_{eq} = \frac{L_E}{24V_{cc}} = \frac{7500}{24 \times 24} = 13.02 \text{ A} \tag{7}$$

where $L_E = \frac{7500 \text{ Wh}}{\text{day}}$

Figure 3. PV array model

Figure 4. PV array current-voltage and power-voltage curves. The values correspond to MPP

2.3. MPPT

As explained above, the PV array modeled allows the use of a simple constant-voltage. This MPPT, therefore, seeks to permanently bias the array at $V_{mpp}=24 \text{ V}$. This section further explained the topology adopted for the MPPT. The section also detailed the simulation results for the proposed MPPT.

2.3.1. MPPT topology

The MPPT is essentially a power electronics converter employing a buck converter topology. The circuit is given in Figure 5. The fundamental of MPPT operation is the variation of duty cycle to adjust bias point. For example, an increase in duty cycle of the converter's switch will result in an increased current-draw from the PV array, thus moving its bias point to the left of the characteristic curve. The MPPT design works likewise; feedback control compares the actual PV array voltage to a reference corresponding to V_{mpp} and uses the difference to make the required changes to the duty cycle via a simple amplifier-integrator-comparator chain.

Figure 5. MPPT circuit and control system

2.3.2. MPPT simulation results

The MPPT was run for various load resistance values. The results are presented in Figure 6. MPPT simulation results for R_{load} values 1Ω is presented in Figure 6(a). In Figure 6(b) is for 3Ω , Figure 6(c) for 5Ω , and Figure 6(d) is of 6Ω . They demonstrate that the MPPT is effective in biasing the PV array at MPP.

2.4. The SEBB and charge controller

The SEBB consists of parallel sets, with two series-connected supercapacitors in each set. The maximum allowed voltage of the SEBB is 10 V and the minimum allowed voltage is 5 V. The charge controller functions as a charge/discharge regulator for the SEBB.

Figures 7 (a) to 7(d) shows the entire PV system with the SEBB and charge controller incorporated. However, Figure 7(a) demonstrates OrCAD construction of final PV system, Figure 7(b) SEBB, and Figure 7(c) control scheme for the SEBB charge controller. The charge controller utilizes a bidirectional buck-boost topology to facilitate two-way power flow. Two switches, S2 and S1, correspond to buck and boost mode respectively. Each switch, operated by pulse-width modulation (PWM) signal, has its own independent control scheme. S1 permits the SEBB to discharge stored energy into the load in boost mode and is operated by a PWM signal generated by the discharge control system. S2 permits the SEBB to absorb energy from load side in buck mode and is operated by a PWM signal generated by the charge control system. Both control systems work similarly, using a simple amplifier-integrator-comparator chain to compare the actual load voltage to a reference corresponding to $V_{rated} = 12$ V, and using the error to adjust the duty cycle of the PWM signal.

The control systems are in turn driven by a simple TTL-based decision system. This decision system monitors load voltage and decides which mode, buck (charge) or boost (discharge), the charge controller should operate in. It then activates the correct control system for this mode of operation, while keeping the other one off. For example, if an overvoltage is detected by the decision system, it will activate the charge control system, which in turn will drive switch S2 (buck mode) at the correct duty cycle so that the excess power is diverted to the SEBB and load voltage is brought down to 12 V.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 6. MPPT simulation results for R_{load} values of (a) 1Ω , (b) 3Ω , (c) 5Ω , and (d) of 6Ω

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 7. OrCAD construction of (a) final PV system, (b) SEBB, and (c) control scheme for the SEBB charge controller

In the meantime, the discharge control system is kept off so as not to interfere with the corrective action. The reverse occurs in the case of undervoltage. A second but important role of the decision system is to protect the SEBB from overcharging and undercharging. It can allow discharge to occur if, and only if, the SEBB voltage

is greater than the 5 V minimum. Likewise, charging can only be allowed if, and only if, the SEBB voltage is less than the 10 V maximum. The algorithm of the charge controller is illustrated in Figure 8. V_{load} refers to the load voltage, while V_{SEBB} is the SEBB voltage.

Figure 8. SEBB charge controller algorithm

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Explaining the MPPT simulation results (given previously) show that the MPPT has an efficiency of around 90%, providing 54 W to the load. Thus, effectively, supply is $P_{supply} = 54$ W. The (2) can be used to find the demanded power, P_{demand} . Thus, if $R_{load} > 2.67 \Omega$, then $P_{demand} < P_{supply}$, and overvoltage occurs. Similarly, if $R_{load} < 2.67 \Omega$, then $P_{demand} > P_{supply}$, and undervoltage occurs. The system is simulated under a variety of load demand conditions achieved by varying R_{load} .

3.1. Overvoltage response

A test of the system's ability to handle overvoltage is carried out. In the simulation, a low demand ($R_{load} = 8 \Omega$) is introduced at time 50 ms to trigger an overvoltage (prior to this, a load of $R_{load} = 2.67 \Omega$ ensured that demand matched supply). The SEBB consists of 8 supercapacitors and has an initial voltage of 9 V. The response is illustrated in Figure 9. The sudden increase in load voltage at 50 ms is clearly visible, as is its quick reduction to 12 V as the supercapacitors absorbed the excess power.

Figure 9. System handling of overvoltage

3.2. Undervoltage response

In this simulation, excessive demand ($R_{load} = 1.75 \Omega$) is introduced at time 50 ms to trigger an undervoltage (prior to this, a load of $R_{load} = 2.67 \Omega$ ensures that demand matches supply). The SEBB consists of 8 supercapacitors and is initially fully charged at 10 V. The response is illustrated in Figure 10. The sudden drop in load voltage as soon as demand is increased is apparent. The system is seen to respond promptly, discharging the supercapacitors into the load to meet the demand and re-achieve 12 V.

Figure 10. System handling of undervoltage

3.3. Test run

A period of low demand ($R_{load} = 5.6 \Omega$) is simulated for 200 ms, followed by a period of excessive demand ($R_{load} = 1.75 \Omega$) for another 200 ms. The SEBB consists of 8 supercapacitors and has voltage 9 V initially. The results are shown in Figure 11. The test run demonstrates the efficacy of the SEBB and charge controller system in absorbing power disequilibria to stabilize load voltage, as well as the ability of the MPPT to continually bias the PV array at MPP.

Figure 11. System response in test run

3.4. Effect of SEBB voltage on undervoltage response

The effect of the SEBB's level of charge on the response during a period of excessive load demand is investigated. A high-demand load of $R_{load} = 1.75 \Omega$ creates an undervoltage situation. This scenario is simulated, first with a 4-supercapacitor SEBB of 8 V initial voltage, and then with 10 V initial voltage. Comparison of the undervoltage responses with initial SEBB voltages of 8 and 10 V are presented in Figures 12(a) and 12(b) respectively.

The results show that the higher level of charge corrects the load voltage for longer and in a smoother manner. Therefore, a higher SEBB voltage is desirable for good undervoltage management. The reasons for this are twofold; firstly, the significantly larger storage in 10 V compared to 8 V (energy is proportional square of voltage), and secondly, the improved performance of the boost converter when there is a higher input voltage; the former explains the longer duration of voltage stability in the case of 10 V initial voltage, and the latter explains the relative smoothness of the load voltage. Another performance aspect demonstrated by these results is the protection provided to the SEBB: in the 8 V initial voltage situation, the system stops SEBB discharge once its minimum allowed voltage of 5 V is reached.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12. Comparison of the undervoltage responses with initial SEBB voltages of (a) 8 V and (b) 10 V

3.5. Possible improvements

Figure 13 illustrates a scenario where the SEBB cannot absorb excess supply power because it is fully charged, thus forcing the load to bear the overvoltage. In practice, an overvoltage could seriously damage a load, and such a situation should be avoided at all costs. To prevent this situation in the PV system, the MPPT control scheme can be upgraded to monitor the load voltage and SEBB state of charge and bias the PV array at a sufficiently lower power output if the SEBB is full and an overvoltage presents itself across the load. A simpler, but less dependable, solution would be to use a large number of supercapacitors in the SEBB such that a fully charged situation is unlikely to occur.

Figure 13. Scenario where SEBB is unable to absorb excess supply power due to fully charged state

4. CONCLUSION

The results demonstrate that the MPPT is able to effectively bias the PV array at MPP. More importantly, the dedicated analog charge controller effectively controls the energy flow in and out of the SEBB to regulate the load voltage at 12 V. This analog system, therefore, shows positive results in improving the efficiency of PV systems. It also demonstrates that incorporation of supercapacitor storage in a PV system provides equilibrium of supply and demand power, thus stabilizing load voltage. This small-scale system can be used as the basis for large-scale PV systems, both grid-connected and standalone. For example, it could be used to power a home or a community of homes during daytime with the grid supplying the night-time demand.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors are indebted to all the contributing institutions for supporting the research. The authors are thankful to the management of the institutions for their support.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Eswam and P. L. Chapman, "Comparison of photovoltaic array maximum power point tracking techniques," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 439–449, Jun. 2007, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2006.874230.
- [2] J. J. Schoeman and J. D. Wyk, "A simplified maximal power controller for terrestrial photovoltaic panel arrays," in *1982 IEEE Power Electronics Specialists conference*, Jun. 1982, pp. 361–367, doi: 10.1109/PESC.1982.7072429.
- [3] Z. Cabrane, J. Kim, K. Yoo, and M. Ouassaid, "HESS-based photovoltaic/batteries/supercapacitors: Energy management strategy and DC bus voltage stabilization," *Solar Energy*, vol. 216, pp. 551–563, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2021.01.048.
- [4] A. Tariq and M. S. J. Asghar, "Development of an analog maximum power point tracker for photovoltaic panel," in *2005 International Conference on Power Electronics and Drives Systems*, 2005, vol. 1, pp. 251–255, doi: 10.1109/PEDS.2005.1619694.
- [5] B. Bekker and H. J. Beukes, "Finding an optimal PV panel maximum power point tracking method," in *2004 IEEE Africon. 7th Africon Conference in Africa (IEEE Cat. No.04CH37590)*, 2004, vol. 01, pp. 1125–1129, doi: 10.1109/AFRICON.2004.1406864.
- [6] T. Noguchi, S. Togashi, and R. Nakamoto, "Short-current pulse based adaptive maximum-power-point tracking for photovoltaic power generation system," in *ISIE'2000. Proceedings of the 2000 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (Cat. No.00TH8543)*, 2000, vol. 1, pp. 157–162, doi: 10.1109/ISIE.2000.930504.

- [7] S. Yuvarajan and S. Xu, "Photovoltaic power converter with a simple maximum-power-point-tracker," in *Proceedings of the 2003 International Symposium on Circuits and Systems, 2003. ISCAS '03*, 2003, vol. 3, pp. III-399–III-402, doi: 10.1109/ISCAS.2003.1205040.
- [8] Y. Kim, H. Jo, and D. Kim, "A new peak power tracker for cost-effective photovoltaic power system," in *IECEC 96. Proceedings of the 31st Intersociety Energy Conversion Engineering Conference*, 1996, vol. 3, pp. 1673–1678, doi: 10.1109/IECEC.1996.553353.
- [9] E. Koutroulis, K. Kalaitzakis, and N. C. Voulgaris, "Development of a microcontroller-based, photovoltaic maximum power point tracking control system," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 46–54, Jan. 2001, doi: 10.1109/63.903988.
- [10] W. Xiao and W. G. Dunford, "A modified adaptive hill climbing MPPT method for photovoltaic power systems," in *2004 IEEE 35th Annual Power Electronics Specialists Conference (IEEE Cat. No.04CH37511)*, 2004, pp. 1957–1963, doi: 10.1109/PESC.2004.1355417.
- [11] L. Zhang, "Real-time maximum power point tracking for grid-connected photovoltaic systems," in *8th International Conference on Power Electronics and Variable Speed Drives*, 2000, vol. 2000, pp. 124–129, doi: 10.1049/cp:20000232.
- [12] Y.-T. Hsiao and C.-H. Chen, "Maximum power tracking for photovoltaic power system," in *Conference Record of the 2002 IEEE Industry Applications Conference. 37th IAS Annual Meeting (Cat. No.02CH37344)*, 2002, vol. 2, pp. 1035–1040, doi: 10.1109/IAS.2002.1042685.
- [13] T. Tafticht and K. Agbossou, "Development of a MPPT method for photovoltaic systems," in *Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering 2004 (IEEE Cat. No.04CH37513)*, 2004, pp. 1123–1126, doi: 10.1109/CCECE.2004.1345317.
- [14] N. Femia, G. Petrone, G. Spagnuolo, and M. Vitelli, "Optimization of perturb and observe maximum power point tracking method," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 963–973, Jul. 2005, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2005.850975.
- [15] K. H. Hussein, "Maximum photovoltaic power tracking: an algorithm for rapidly changing atmospheric conditions," *IEE Proceedings - Generation, Transmission and Distribution*, vol. 142, no. 1, pp. 59–64, 1995, doi: 10.1049/ip-gtd:19951577.
- [16] T.-Y. Kim, H.-G. Ahn, S. K. Park, and Y.-K. Lee, "A novel maximum power point tracking control for photovoltaic power system under rapidly changing solar radiation," in *ISIE 2001. 2001 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics Proceedings (Cat. No.01TH8570)*, 2001, vol. 2, pp. 1011–1014, doi: 10.1109/ISIE.2001.931613.
- [17] Y.-C. Kuo, T.-J. Liang, and J.-F. Chen, "Novel maximum-power-point-tracking controller for photovoltaic energy conversion system," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 594–601, Jun. 2001, doi: 10.1109/41.925586.
- [18] C. Raga, A. Barrado, I. Quesada, A. Lazaro, C. Anocibar, and J. F. Sierra, "Comparison of two different electrical power architecture for electric vehicles applications based on fuel cell and supercapacitors," in *2008 IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference*, Jun. 2008, pp. 1326–1330, doi: 10.1109/PESC.2008.4592117.
- [19] P. Phoosomma, N. Kasayapanand, and N. Mungkung, "Combination of supercapacitor and AC power source in storing and supplying energy for computer backup power," *Journal of Electrical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 993–1000, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s42835-018-00070-0.
- [20] F. Nadeem, S. M. S. Hussain, P. K. Tiwari, A. K. Goswami, and T. S. Ustun, "Comparative review of energy storage systems, their roles, and impacts on future power systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 4555–4585, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2888497.
- [21] V. Skiparev, R. Machlev, N. R. Chowdhury, Y. Levron, E. Petlenkov, and J. Belikov, "Virtual inertia control methods in islanded microgrids," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 6, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14061562.
- [22] R. A. Hanifah, S. F. Toha, S. Ahmad, and M. K. Hassan, "Swarm-intelligence tuned current reduction for power-assisted steering control in electric vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 7202–7210, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2017.2784344.
- [23] K. A. Khan and M. Khalid, "Improving the transient response of hybrid energy storage system for voltage stability in DC microgrids using an autonomous control strategy," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 10460–10472, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3051144.
- [24] B. Diarra, A. M. Zungeru, S. Ravi, J. Chuma, B. Basutli, and I. Zibani, "Design of a photovoltaic system with ultracapacitor energy buffer," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 33, pp. 216–223, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.promfg.2019.04.026.
- [25] S. S. Rama and M. Rajini, "Energy management system with a reduced sensor for DC microgrid," in *2021 Innovations in Energy Management and Renewable Resources (52042)*, Feb. 2021, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/IEMRE52042.2021.9386728.
- [26] P. Nambisan and M. Khanra, "Optimal energy management of battery supercapacitor aided solar PV powered agricultural feed mill using pontryagin's minimum principle," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, pp. 1–1, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2021.3104347.
- [27] M. F. Elmorshedy, M. R. Elkadeem, K. M. Kotb, I. B. M. Taha, and D. Mazzeo, "Optimal design and energy management of an isolated fully renewable energy system integrating batteries and supercapacitors," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 245, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2021.114584.
- [28] Y. M. Al-Humaid, K. A. Khan, M. A. Abdulgalil, and M. Khalid, "Two-stage stochastic optimization of sodium-sulfur energy storage technology in hybrid renewable power systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 162962–162972, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3133261.
- [29] M. D. Keshavarzi and M. H. Ali, "Dynamic performance enhancement of power grids by operating solar photovoltaic (PV) system as supercapacitor energy storage," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 14, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14144277.
- [30] B. R. Ravada and N. R. Tummuru, "Control of a supercapacitor-battery-PV based stand-alone DC-microgrid," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 1268–1277, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2020.2982425.
- [31] M. Elsis, M. Aboelela, M. Soliman, and W. Mansour, "Design of optimal model predictive controller for LFC of nonlinear multi-area power system with energy storage devices," *Electric Power Components and Systems*, vol. 46, no. 11–12, pp. 1300–1311, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1080/15325008.2018.1469056.
- [32] M. Elsis, "New design of robust PID controller based on meta-heuristic algorithms for wind energy conversion system," *Wind Energy*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 391–403, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1002/we.2439.
- [33] M. Elsis, "New variable structure control based on different meta-heuristics algorithms for frequency regulation considering nonlinearities effects," *International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems*, vol. 30, no. 7, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1002/2050-7038.12428.
- [34] T. V. Muni and S. V. N. L. Lalitha, "Implementation of control strategies for optimum utilization of solar photovoltaic system with energy storage systems," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 716–726, 2020, doi: 10.20508/ijrer.v10i2.10565.g7943.
- [35] H. Guentri, T. Allaoui, M. Mekki, and M. Denai, "Power management and control of a photovoltaic system with hybrid battery-supercapacitor energy storage based on heuristics methods," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 39, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2021.102578.

- [36] A. Abdelkader, A. Rabeih, D. Mohamed Ali, and J. Mohamed, "Multi-objective genetic algorithm-based sizing optimization of a stand-alone wind/PV power supply system with enhanced battery/supercapacitor hybrid energy storage," *Energy*, vol. 163, pp. 351–363, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2018.08.135.
- [37] L. Castañer and S. Silvestre, *Modelling photovoltaic systems using PSpice®*. Wiley, 2002, doi: 10.1002/0470855541.
- [38] A. M. Zungeru *et al.*, "Design of photovoltaic system for IoT devices," in *Green Internet of Things Sensor Networks*, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 55–81, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-54983-1_4.
- [39] POWERSIM, "Powersim technology," *POWERSIM (Software for Power Electronics Simulation)*, 2018. <https://powersimtech.com/products/psim/> (accessed Nov. 02, 2019).

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Savari R. Sahaya Prabakaran is a full Professor and CEO and Founder of Inventus BioEnergy, India. He was a Joint Director in the Directorate of Research, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai, India, and was the Dean of School of Electronics Engineering (SENSE), VIT University, Chennai campus, from August 2015 to August 2018. He has worked with Manipal International University in Malaysia, the University of Nottingham Malaysia/UK campuses, and CSIR National Laboratories (NAL and CECRI). He is the recipient of the young scientist award in the year 1994. He spent significant time in France and US labs and Universities as Post-Doctoral Fellow and technology consultant. He has served as a faculty member in various international universities, including the University of Malaya, Universiti Teknologi Petronas and Multimedia University, UPMC, Paris, UPIV, Amiens, France, and Tohoku University, Japan. He has also served as an adjunct professor in Malaysia University of Science and Technology and Manipal International University, Malaysia. He has served on various expert committees in Malaysia (Multimedia Development Corporation and office of Prime Minister Department (UNIK) and FP7 European Union committee). He was the technical consultant to United States Army research project under Southern University, Baton Rouge, USA. He was the recipient of the prestigious Erasmus Mundus visiting scholar under the European Union (EU) and held a visiting professorship in France. He is also the recipient of the UK-Singapore visiting scientist award in 2007 in the University of Sheffield, UK. Recently, he has held a visiting professorship in Tohoku University, Japan. Dr. Prabakaran has received several research grants from DST, DRDO, Young Scientist grant scheme, Malaysian government grant (MOSTI and MOHE), and Motorola Inc., USA. His expertise focuses on supercapacitors for a variety of applications including naval missiles (DRDO). His current research interests include Memristors and Neuristors as well. He has delivered over 52 invited/keynote talks in international scientific conferences/symposia. He has edited a few research books and has been the guest editor for international journals as well. He served as a consultant to the battery and supercapacitor industries. He has published over 75 high impact journal papers and over 200 conference papers and holds international granted patents (Malaysia, USA, and Japan). He is known for his notable research in the areas of power sources (Li-Ion batteries and supercapacitors), RF energy harvesting, advanced power solutions for IoT systems and memristors. He can be contacted at email: srsprabakaran1611@gmail.com.

Adamu M. Zungeru received the Ph.D., MSc, and BEng from Nottingham University, UK, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria Nigeria, and Federal University of Technology Minna Nigeria, respectively. He was a Research Fellow at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in the USA, where he also obtained a Postgraduate Teaching Certificate in 2014. He is currently serving as a Professor and the Head of the Department of Electrical, Computer, and Telecommunications Engineering at the Botswana International University of Science and Technology (BIUST). Before joining BIUST in 2015, he was a Senior Lecturer and Head of the Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department at Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria. Prof. Adamu Murtala Zungeru is a Senior Member of the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), a registered engineer with the Council for The Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN), a Professional Engineer registered with the Botswana Engineers Registration Board (ERB), and Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) in the USA. He is the Inventor of a Termite-hill routing algorithm for wireless sensor networks and has three of his Patent applications registered with the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). He has also authored 5 Academic books and over 60 international research articles in reputable Journals, including the IEEE Systems Journal, IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Access, JNCA-Elsevier, and others, with over 1000 citations and an H-Index of 15. He is at present serving as an Associate Editor to IEEE Access Journal. He has also served as an international reviewer to IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics, IEEE Sensors, IEEE Access, IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, and IEEE Transactions Sustainable Computing, JNCA-ELSEVIER, and numerous others. He has also served as the Chairman of the IEEE Botswana Sub-Section (2019-2020). He can be contacted at: zungerum@biust.ac.bw.

Bokani Mtengi received her PhD and MEng in Electrical Engineering from Howard University, U.S.A and her BEng in Biomedical Engineering from University of Hartford, U.S.A. She joined Botswana International University of Science and Technology as a Lecturer in the Department of Electrical, Computer and Telecommunications engineering in 2018. She is presently a Senior Lecturer Her teaching and research interests are in power electronics, energy systems and bioelectronics. She worked as an Electron Microscopy Imaging Engineer at Howard Hughes Medical Research Lab from 2016-2018. She was employed as a Biomedical engineer from 2004 to 2007 by the Ministry of Health, Botswana. She is the current the Secretary of the IEEE Botswana Subsection, and the country representative of the IEEE Women in Power (WiP) Southern region. She can be contacted at email: mtengib@biuts.ac.bw.

Siluvai M. Michael is an Associate Professor in the Chemical Sciences Research Centre, Department of Chemistry, Sri Sivasubramaniya Nadar College of Engineering, Kalavakkam, Chennai, India. She received her PhD in 1996 in the field of corrosion from Madurai Kamaraj University, India. She also worked as a research fellow in the Central Electrochemical Research Institute (CECRI), a premier national laboratory in India. She then continued her post-doctoral fellowship at the Universiti Malaya, Multimedia University, Malaysia, and Université Pierre et Marie Curie, France, developing lithium-ion batteries. Dr. Michael has published more than 40 international peer-reviewed journal articles and has a few international patents to her credit. She has served on advisory boards and delivered invited talks in international conferences. Her expertise includes corrosion aspects of intermetallic alloys, hybrid supercapacitors, nanomaterials, lithium batteries, and Li-air batteries. She can be contacted at email: michaelm@ssn.edu.in.